

A Modular Deep Learning Framework for Scene Understanding in Augmented Reality Applications

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Abstract—Taking as input natural images and videos, augmented reality (AR) applications aim to enhance the real world with superimposed digital contents, enabling interaction between the user and the environment. One important step in this process is automatic scene analysis and understanding, which should be performed both in real time and with a good level of object recognition accuracy. In this work, an end-to-end framework based on the combination of a Super Resolution network with a detection and recognition deep network has been proposed to increase performance and lower processing time. This novel approach has been evaluated on two different datasets: the popular COCO dataset, whose real images are used for benchmarking many different computer vision tasks, and a generated dataset with synthetic images recreating a variety of environmental, lighting, and acquisition conditions. The evaluation analysis is focused on small objects, which are more challenging to correctly detect and recognise. The results show that the Average Precision is higher for small and low-resolution objects for the proposed end-to-end approach in most of the selected conditions.

Index Terms—Augmented Reality, Object Detection, Scene Analysis, Scene Understanding, Object Recognition, Deep Learning, Super-Resolution, Feature Extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

Augmented Reality (AR) applications enable users to interact with their surrounding environment by overlaying digital visuals on top of reality through the camera view. The aim is to enhance the real world through the combination of virtual information, such as text, images, video, or 3D models, with scenes captured by a camera in real time [36]. Furthermore, recent advances in computer systems' capabilities, high-speed communication, and computer vision technologies have boosted the demand for human-digital interaction through Mixed Reality (XR) headsets and new three-dimensional interactive displays. The rapid development of AR technologies has fostered their application to different fields such as restoration, education, archaeology, art, tourism, commerce, and healthcare. [39].

These immersive technologies rely on the analysis of the surrounding environment to extract content information. For

instance, in the field of autonomous vehicles, scene analysis and understanding (e.g., vehicle detection, traffic signs and light recognition, and pedestrian detection) is a key component for decision-making tasks and end-to-end control [29] so that the augmented environment can be seamlessly visualised on the car display.

In the last decades, advances in computer vision have fostered the design and implementation of object recognition methods, increasing computational performance and lowering process time [43]. As a result, current AR technologies based on object recognition use complex computer vision techniques to detect and track objects in the real world. Examples of such technologies include the You Only Look Once (YOLO) model [1], homomorphic filtering and Haar markers [15] and the Single Shot Detector [8]. The use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Deep Learning (DL) led to faster and more accurate detection processes [41]. However, they still deliver poor performance when camera resolution is low or when the objects to recognise are very small or far away. Thus, this can have an impact on scene understanding and the overall AR experience.

The aim of this study is to provide a novel integrated end-to-end solution that improves performance in such conditions by introducing Super-Resolution (SR) mechanisms. Not only have Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) been used for new data generation and to study adversarial samples and attacks, but in the recent past they have also been investigated to perform SR tasks [6] [18]. Inspired by this, the proposed approach is based on a cascade of two connected networks. The first network is a super-resolution network that takes as input transformed images. More specifically, a 3D representation is used where the z-axis represents the colour channel of the image. The second network is based on the YOLO series' architecture, which was designed to improve performance at a low computational cost. The key contributions of this work are: a) the end-to-end design and training of the two connected networks, allowing automatic minimisation of the

SR reconstruction error and maximisation of the detection and classification accuracy with a single novel optimisation function; b) a complete comparative study under a variety of environmental conditions that are known to affect the overall performance of AR devices; and c) a new dataset composed of synthetic objects created under different conditions, which allows unbiased performance evaluation under different sensor and environmental parameters. The aforementioned solutions could be integrated into the AR applications as a remote cloud service for better scene understanding or, perhaps, as an offline solution.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 1 introduces the problem and relevant technologies; Section 2 provides an overview of related work; Section 3 describes the proposed end-to-end architecture; Section 4 presents results obtained using both a real image dataset (COCO) and a novel synthetic image dataset; and Section 4 draws the final conclusions.

II. OVERVIEW OF PREVIOUS WORK

Augmented reality applications rely on machine learning and computer vision techniques to recognise the presence of physical objects in the real world so that virtual objects can be added and rendered in real time. In recent years, the use of Deep CNNs has significantly improved the performance and accuracy of computer vision for many tasks, such as object detection and recognition. In 2014, Girshick et al. proposed the Regions with CNN features (RCNN) for object detection [14]. First, initial object candidate boxes are extracted by a selective search. Then, each box is rescaled to a fixed-size image that is fed to a CNN model trained on an AlexNet [37] for feature extraction. Finally, object detection is performed using a linear SVM classifier. Although this approach led to a significant improvement in the mean Average Precision when compared with previous approaches, it suffers from slow detection speed. To overcome this issue, He et al. proposed the Spatial Pyramid Pooling Network (SPPNet) [19]. Its main novelty is a Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) layer, which generates a fixed-length representation regardless of image size and scale, allowing images of varying sizes to be fed during the training process, which improves scale invariance and reduces overfitting. In the case of object detection, the feature maps are computed from the entire image only once, and then the features are aggregated in sub-regions to generate fixed-length vectors for training the detectors. Evaluation of this method showed that it could detect objects 24 to 102 times faster than RCNN. In 2015, Girshick proposed an improved version of the previous RCNN architecture called the Fast RCNN detector [13]. Although this network allows to train a detector and a bounding box regression simultaneously with the same network configuration, slow speed remained an issue. The same year, Ren et al. proposed the Faster RCNN detector [34], which is considered the first almost real-time deep learning detector using an end-to-end training. This architecture introduces a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to speed up the detection process. Numerous variants of this approach

have been suggested in the following years to decrease any computational redundancy [7] [23] [24].

In particular, Cao et al. (2020) proposed a method called D2Det [4], which is based on the Faster R-CNN framework. Here the Region of Interest (ROI) features are processed through two different stages: a high-density local regression, which replaces the Faster RCNN offset regression, and a discriminant ROI pooling. In contrast to all the methods mentioned above, which are considered two-stage detectors as they perform a coarse to fine process, in 2016, Joseph et al. proposed a one-stage detector called You Only Look Once (YOLO) [31]. The image is divided into regions, and the network predicts bounding boxes for each region at the same time. With such an approach, the whole process is completed in one step by applying a single network to the entire image, increasing processing speed significantly. Although YOLO's second and third versions have improved its prediction accuracy [32] [33], they still underperform in terms of localisation accuracy when compared with the two-stage methods. Liu et al. tried to improve this aspect by proposing a Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) [27] introducing a multi-reference and multi-resolution detection method detecting objects at different scales on different network layers. As a result, the SSD network gains a small improvement, outperforming YOLO in the PASCAL VOC detection task [9]. Suggesting that extreme foreground-background class imbalance is the cause of the lower accuracy of the one-stage detectors, in 2018, Lin et al. introduced the RetinaNet [25] where a new loss function called "focal loss" was added to improve their approach. Indeed, by modifying the standard cross-entropy loss, the detector is more attentive to misclassified examples during training. A recent trend in object detection methods is anchor-free techniques, where the methods infer the bounding box corners instead of fixed bounding boxes. A notable example is CenterNet, proposed by Zhou et al [42]. The CenterNet method is a state-of-the-art Lidar-based 3D detection and tracking framework. It could be viewed as an improvement over CornerNet, which is an anchor-free approach to detecting bounding boxes as a pair of keypoints. The keypoints are the top-left and bottom-right corners retrieved via the corner pooling technique introduced by the same authors [21]. The CenterNet method has introduced the notion of a centre keypoint to help associating the corner keypoints with an object in the image. The CenterNet method has outperformed common anchor-based solutions such as Faster RCNN and YOLO by a significant margin. In 2020, Perez-Rua et al. [30] introduced OpeN-ended Center nEt (ONCE), which offered functionality that can detect objects from classes with a small number of examples inside its training dataset. The more recent approaches start to investigate the possibilities of transformers covered in the DEtection TRansformer (DETR) method [5], with the advantage of being simple yet on par with the rest of the detection techniques used in the field. Later, Zhu et al. proposed Deformable DETR as an improvement to address the performance problem in detecting small objects and achieve state-of-the-art performance.

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed novel framework trained end-to-end. For the SR and detector models any state-of-the-art solutions can be used without affecting the overall pipeline and the proposed modular architecture.

Fig. 2: Training setup for the DAT SR deep network.

Fig. 3: YOLOX architecture relying on a decoupled head

Fig. 4: An example of predictions and Confusion Matrix (the white colour of the image was levelled up to see the numbers)

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

In parallel, approaches have been developed to enhance the detection of small objects, which is particularly challenging as they have fewer visible details. Super-resolution solutions relying on Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) [16] have proved particularly successful [2] [22]. Indeed, their competitive process involving two neural networks, i.e., a generator network and a discriminant network, ensures that the generated images are as realistic as possible.

Herein, we address the detection and recognition of visually small objects by proposing a novel approach based on a super-resolution network and a second network with a modified YOLO architecture trained end-to-end. This solution aims to provide accurate detection of objects that are very small or very far from the camera sensor of the AR glasses while delivering a fast processing time, enabling its usage in real-time applications.

In this paper, we propose an end-to-end framework for scene understanding that combines super-resolution, object detection, and classification architectures. Figure 1 shows an overview of the proposed methodology, where the two main components take as input an image (or a video) and are trained in an end-to-end manner. Details of these two processing blocks are described in the following sections:

A. Super-Resolution Method

As reviewed in Section 2, the usage of super-resolution in a pre-processing stage has been included in many computer vision pipelines. Typically, the super-resolution model is trained in an unsupervised manner using several independent datasets, while the target classification or detection model is trained only on a single task-related dataset. By doing so, some extra information that is not available in the target labelled dataset is injected into the SR images [20].

Fig. 5: Examples of the generated synthetic data. The bottom row represents examples from the Ground category. From the left, the first column shows the Camera sub-category, the second column shows the Light sub-category, the third column displays the Weather sub-category.

SR models are trained under the assumption that the low-scale images, passed as input, are the results of some low-pass filter, such as a Gaussian blur or a point spread function. The training takes place by first down-sampling high-resolution images with such a kernel and then optimising the model to reconstruct these high-resolution images. Theoretically, the kernel function should match the actual blurring process caused by the camera used in the targeted application. However, since this is usually unknown, 'standard' kernels have been used. Unfortunately, these standard kernels fail to model the specific optics and sensors of the actual cameras that captured the images of interest, leading to degraded performance in real-world scenarios. To address this, methods have been proposed to learn the blur kernel, known as Blind Super Resolution [28].

The most accurate approaches, such as the state-of-the-art network Deep Alternating Network (DAT) [20], have relied on deep learning architectures. DAT was selected for our pipeline because its learning is unsupervised, and it delivers fast computation, making it suitable for mobile devices and low-specification desktop computers. In fact, the authors demonstrated that the average speed is 0.75 seconds per image, which is more than 500 times faster than its competitors KernelGAN [3], ZSSR [35], and 5 times faster than IKC [17]. These average speeds are considered fast in the domain of SR. Figure 2 shows DAT's training setup, which consists of two main networks called Restorer and Estimator: the Restorer produces the SR image, while the Estimator provides an estimate of a blur kernel given the restored image. The two networks are used in alternation, improving the quality of the SR image and the accuracy of the estimated kernel at each Restorer-Estimator step. The sequence of Restorer-Estimator is optimised end-to-end using a stochastic back-propagation algorithm.

B. Object Detection Method

For augmented reality applications, object detection models must deliver high accuracy in real-time. For the proposed framework, the anchor-free model, YOLOX [11], offers the best compromise. Its simple, powerful, and computationally efficient architecture is built upon one of the most widely used detectors in the industry, YOLOv3 [33], which not only has a

limited computational cost but also has received excellent software support. However, an important improvement of YOLOX is that, unlike the previous architectures of the YOLO series, it uses a decoupled head, which improves convergence speed. Figure 3 provides an overview of the architecture of YOLOX. Following a 1×1 convolutional layer used to decrease the number of channels, there are two parallel branches with 3×3 convolutional layers. Moreover, compared to the baseline YOLOv3, an Intersection over Union (IoU) aware branch is added in the regression branch.

Another enhancement of YOLOX is, unlike the past versions of YOLO detectors (except for YOLOv1), the usage of an anchor-free model. Anchors are candidate bounding boxes with predefined dimensions that the detector selects during the detection process and for which it predicts the delta values for their centres and dimensions. Obviously, these additional predictions require extra processing during both the training and inference stages, which impacts the overall computational time. On the other hand, when using an anchor-free approach, bounding boxes are predicted directly, which reduces the number of design parameters. As such an approach requires advanced data augmentation to match the performance of anchor-based models, state-of-the-art data augmentation approaches, i.e., Mosaic and MixUp, were exploited [11]. Indeed, they are known to bring stability and reduce overfitting during the training process. Finally, it is important to specify that YOLOX leverages a high-performance CNN front-end, CSPNet [38], which is followed by a feature pyramids network (FPN) [33].

C. End-to-end Framework

The methods described in sub-sections B and C were integrated into an end-to-end framework. Thus, the framework comprises two main components, i.e. Super-Resolution and Detector. Equation (1) illustrates the proposed end-to-end architecture where x is the input low-resolution image, y is the image generated by the super-resolution function $S(\cdot)$, and z is the output of the detection function $D(\cdot)$.

$$\begin{cases} y=S(x) \\ z=D(y) \end{cases} \rightarrow z = D(S(x)) \quad (1)$$

In this framework, an input image is first handled by the SR component, which produces a super-resolved output image. Then, this image is passed to the detector component, which recognises and locates objects. Through this process, the detector learns from images enhanced by the SR component. The input images are super-resolved using kernels. There are many types of kernels, such as the common bicubic kernel or linear kernel. These kernels are well-studied and don't require an AI network to calculate them.

However, in the case of the SR task, real-world images don't contain information about the kernel, making it challenging to successfully restore them. Consequently, an estimator is used to infer the kernel during the training process. This estimated kernel is then passed to the restorer to generate images. As a

result, the restored images contain features that are the product of the kernel. These features can be picked up by the detector during the training process, creating a symbiotic relationship between the SR and detector components, leading to improved performance.

To monitor and evaluate the training of the framework, several state-of-the-art loss functions were selected. The detector is trained using Varifocal Loss [40] as the classification loss function and SIOU [12] (Scylla Intersection over Union) as the box regression loss function. Moreover, the training process was facilitated with SimOTA, a simplification of OTA [10] (Optimal Transport Assignment), for dynamic label assignment [11].

The Varifocal Loss is particularly efficient because it considers both classification and localisation scores when ranking candidates using IoU. Similarly, the SIOU loss function addresses direction mismatch between expected and predicted bounding boxes by exploiting angle, distance, shape, and IoU costs.

Finally, the value of SimOTA is to view the task of bounding box assignment as an optimal transport problem, where the unit transportation cost between an anchor-point and ground truth is expressed as a weighted sum of their classification and regression losses to find the best assignment solution.

D. Parameters

The end-to-end framework was fine-tuned by running 10 epochs with a batch size of 3 on both real and synthetic data under three different categories. While the learning rate was set to 0.0001 for the SR component, it was set to 0.0032 with SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) optimisation for the detector. Additionally, as mentioned earlier, training was enhanced using Mosaic and MixUp as data augmentation strategies.

IV. EVALUATION

The proposed method has been applied to object recognition and scene understanding. Its evaluation was performed using the Common Objects in Context (COCO) dataset [26] and a synthetic dataset where different environmental conditions were applied to affect image quality. COCO is widely used to benchmark computer vision models. It consists of 330K images, with more than 200K labelled images, 1.5 million object instances, 80 object categories, 91 stuff categories, and 5 captions per image.

Comparisons with state-of-the-art methods rely on the mean Average Precision (mAP), a standard metric introduced in 2014 to quantify object detection performance based on a user-defined set of criteria [26]. It is defined as the mean value of the average precision of the individual classes:

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n AP_k \quad (2)$$

where AP_k is Average Precision of class k , and n is the number of classes.

TABLE I: Model Performance on the COCO Dataset in terms of mAP (%)

RetinaNet	YOLOv3	Faster R-CNN	Proposed
52.61	44.76	40.50	67.09

TABLE II: Model Performance on the Synthetic Dataset according to the Three Image Categories

Category	mAP(%)
Camera	60.52
Light	81.25
Weather	66.98

In this evaluation process, using the COCO dataset, Table I shows the performance in terms of mAP of the proposed framework compared to other approaches presented in the literature review. Our framework outperforms all its competitors. Moreover, the added value of the super-resolution component is clearly established as it exceeds YOLO’s mAP by over 20%. The confusion matrix in Figure 4 further demonstrates the performance of the model. In particular, it predicts objects belonging to the prevailing “car” category with high accuracy. However, it should be highlighted that the “van” category is often mistaken for the “car” category, which is due to the visual similarity between images of these two classes.

Further evaluation has been conducted using a synthetic dataset that we created using a 3D Rendering Engine. This dataset consists of approximately 3000 low-resolution images per category of ground vehicles in different environments and weather conditions. An example of the dataset with predictions can be seen in Figure 5. The images in this dataset belong to three different categories, each allowing us to assess our model on specific properties: a) Camera, b) Light, c) Weather.

The “Camera” category contains images of objects captured from various camera angles and distances. In the “Light” category, images are generated under a variety of lighting parameters, mimicking different parts of the day such as morning, afternoon, evening, and night. The “Weather” category simulates images captured under diverse weather circumstances, including varying rain and wind conditions.

The performance of the proposed framework for these three categories in terms of mAP is shown in Table II. Additionally, the confusion matrices can be observed in Figure 6. As could be observed, the results demonstrate high confidence in predicting the buses and cars categories. The sport cars and cars categories are quite often mistaken what is reasonable because both categories are very similar. The van category on the other hand sometimes has been mistaken with the sport cars category what indicates close similarity of the samples in the dataset. Whereas the bus category samples seem to be distinct enough to avoid confusion with the other categories.

V. CONCLUSION

The work presented in this paper offers an end-to-end solution for object detection and recognition on AR devices. The modular architecture allows for the integration of different SR and detection models within the same pipeline. The paper

provides an overview of existing solutions and approaches in both super resolution and scene analysis methods, specifically focusing on their applications in immersive environments.

The proposed architecture was tested on both real and synthetic datasets in a comparative study, alongside other state-of-the-art approaches. The results obtained demonstrate a significant improvement, particularly for low-resolution or distant objects. Furthermore, the proposed framework was evaluated and analysed under various environmental conditions and with a range of camera sensors.

In addition to the evaluation on real datasets, a new balanced synthetic dataset was generated. This dataset includes annotated data covering multiple objects and environments, allowing for further assessment and experimentation.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10047653] and funded by the European Union [under EC Horizon Europe grant agreement number 101070181 (TALON)].

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(a) Ground Category - Camera Subcategory - Confusion Matrix

(b) Ground Category - Light Subcategory - Confusion Matrix

(c) Ground Category - Weather Subcategory - Confusion Matrix

(d) Ground Category - Camera Subcategory - Super Confusion Matrix

(e) Ground Category - Light Subcategory - Super Confusion Matrix

(f) Ground Category - Weather Subcategory - Super Confusion Matrix

Fig. 6: Confusion Matrices of the Ground category of the generated synthetic data. From the left, the first column shows the Camera sub-category, the second column shows the Light sub-category, the third columns displays the Weather sub-category.

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